

Policy Recommendations BIM-Based Building Permit in Europe

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16688219

Funded by the
European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101056973

UK Participants in Horizon Europe Project ACCORD are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10040207 (Cardiff University), 10038999 (Birmingham City University and 10049977 (Building Smart International)

Glossary

ACCC	Automated Code-Compliance Check
AEC3PO	Architecture, Engineering, and Construction Compliance Checking and Permitting Ontology
API	Application Programming Interface
DBL	Digital Building Logbook
BCF	Building Collaboration Format
BCRL	Building Compliance Rule Language
BIM	Building Information Modeling
EIR	Exchange Information Requirements
GRAPHDB	Semantic Graph Database
GIS	Geographic Information System
IDS	Information Delivery Specification
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
NLP	Natural Language Processing
RASE	Requirement, Applicability, Selection and Exception
R&D	Research and Development
YAML-LD	Yet Another Multicolumn Layout for Linked Data

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Introduction

The Building Permit is a key tool used by public authorities to ensure that construction, renovation, or demolition projects comply with local building codes, zoning regulations, and safety standards. Across Europe, the digitalisation of Building Permit processes is gradually gaining momentum. Traditional paper-based systems are being replaced with online platforms, making it easier to access documentation, track permit applications, and communicate among stakeholders. While this shift represents significant progress, the integration of Building Information Modelling (BIM) into the Building Permit process is expected to have an even greater impact. BIM will enhance transparency, reduce processing time, and increase overall efficiency.

The EU funded ACCORD project has explored the new frontiers of the implementation of BIM in Building permit processes developing a framework that includes semantic interoperability, a rule formalisation tool, and integrated microservices for digital building permit and compliance checking processes that were demonstrated in 13 Use Cases in five real-life construction projects around Europe: Finland, Estonia, Germany, the UK, and Spain.

This Policy Recommendation is based on the findings of the ACCORD project. It highlights the recommendations written in the ACCORD Transformation Pathways Report, supported by the Landscape Review report, the ACCORD framework and user-required specification and analysis of lessons learned from the country demonstrations in the ACCORD Best Practices of Modern Digital Building Permitting Processes in Europe.

These recommendations aim to contribute to the European Commission Strategy for Housing Construction, the New European Bauhaus Initiative and the Build4People partnership by bridging the gap between research and practice and proposing evidence-based information for policymaking, contributing to the future of BIM-based Building Permits in Europe.

What is a BIM-Based Building Permit?

A **BIM-based building permit** refers to a building permit issued through the submission of Building Information Modelling (BIM). For a permit to be a **BIM-based building permit**, the BIM model must be the main source of data and geometry information for both permit submission and regulatory checking. For the issuing of a **BIM-based building permit**, the approval process is informed by semi-automated and automated building regulations compliance checks. Semi-automated BIM model checks facilitate the initial review and validation of the models, while automated BIM model checks ensure comprehensive and accurate compliance with the regulations. Regulations compliance checks tools require inputs from machine-readable regulations and standards. A BIM-based building permit can streamline specific stages of the process, while the overall approval process remains broader in scope.

Why BIM-Based Building Permit?

The BIM-based Building Permit process can bring several benefits to all parties involved in the building approval request as follows.

A More Consistent and Reliable Source of Information

BIM models consolidate all project data into a centralised, accessible format, as a single source of truth, reducing discrepancies and ensuring all stakeholders have consistent and reliable information for different regulatory requirements and processes. These models provide customers with valuable insights after construction, serving multiple purposes throughout the building's lifecycle.

A More Transparent Process and Faster Information Exchange

BIM-based building permits create a clear digital audit history, simplifying future reference for compliance or updates. BIM models include extensive metadata about materials, systems, and design elements, making regulatory reviews more thorough and transparent. Also, provides a harmonised framework for model assessments and limiting individual interpretations on the applicants and municipality's side.

Faster Approvals with Reduced Errors

BIM models enable automated compliance checks against building codes and regulations, drastically reducing manual review time. Automated processes minimise the risk of oversight or misinterpretation of plans, ensuring precise assessments.

A More Efficient Collaboration Between the Parties

BIM permits facilitate direct collaboration between designers, builders, and regulatory authorities, reducing back-and-forth communications. Authorities can provide targeted feedback using the BIM model, helping designers quickly address issues.

Information Integration and Exchange with City Models

Integration of BIM and GIS supports city planning, creating a robust database supporting the city plan.

Better Resource and Competence Use

BIM models and automated regulation compliance checks allow regulatory experts to focus on high-value tasks, such as ensuring safety and design quality, rather than manual compliance checks. Digital models simplify inspections, allowing authorities to concentrate on critical areas. A checking tool integrated with the building permit service allows for random inspections or targeted examination of exceptions by either the designer or the authority.

What are the challenges?

Despite its demonstrated benefits, the integration of BIM into permitting processes has still some challenges to be overcome as follows.

Lack of a Common Vision and Strategy at National Level

A major challenge hindering the widespread adoption of BIM-based permitting is the absence of a unified national vision, resulting from fragmented and inconsistent initiatives at the regional and municipal levels. Without coordinated leadership and standardised guidelines, efforts to implement BIM-based building permits vary significantly across different jurisdictions, leading to disparities in technology adoption, data management, and regulatory practices. This fragmentation creates confusion among stakeholders, limits interoperability, and reduces the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the permitting process.

Lack of Clear Standards and Procedures

The lack of clear standards and procedures put at risk the quality control of BIM models, bring uncertainty in the information required for the delivery of BIM-based building permit models. Designers face difficulties due to unclear guidelines and specifications, which are not consistently integrated into their software tools, hindering seamless implementation.

Risk of Adopting Innovation

Adopting innovation is challenging as it implies change. The lack of understanding of the benefits that the innovation brings to daily work, lack of time to train staff, lack of guidance or support on the process implementation, lack of appropriate resources and planning in the implementation of activities can jeopardise the process.

Lack of Expertise within the Authorities and Applicants

The adoption of information modelling lacks a robust competence framework to support stakeholders. Legislators and authorities, such as fire department officials, often lack sufficient training to effectively understand and utilise information modelling systems.

Lack of Affordable Solutions for Authorities and SMEs

Key challenges include the lack of affordable solutions in the market and the uncertainty over which party will assume financial responsibility for the software required to implement the BIM-based building permit process.

ACCORD Policy Recommendations

ACCORD partners have put together 12 recommendations based on ACCORD project findings

- 1 Development of a Common Vision for a National BIM-Based Building Permitting Strategy
- 2 Standardise an Interoperable Format for the Representation of Construction Regulatory Documents and Rules
- 3 Formalise Machine-Readable Regulations and Building Codes
- 4 Development of a National and Regional Rule Repository
- 5 Implementation of an Interoperable BIM-Based Building Permit Framework Based on Open Standards
- 6 Adoption of an Interoperable Cloud Architecture
- 7 Promote Stakeholder Collaboration
- 8 Support the Transition with Use Case Harmonisation
- 9 Provide Training and Competence Building
- 10 Secure Funding for Digital Transformation
- 11 Implement Feedback Loops and Continuous Improvement
- 12 Address Legal Issues Related to BIM Storage and Ownership

1.

Development of a Common Vision for a National BIM-Based Building Permitting Strategy

The development of a National Digital Strategy for BIM-based building permits should include a comprehensive roadmap to ensure alignment and consistency between national and local levels. This strategy must establish a shared vision and clear objectives and timelines for the implementation of BIM-based building permits at the national scale while taking into account the unique requirements of local contexts. The ultimate goal is to create a solution that addresses all needs for achieving BIM-based building permits and automated code-compliance checks by translating text-based building codes into machine-readable rules, using standardised and common methods that satisfy all stakeholders.

Additionally, a National Built Environment Information System should be established, incorporating new use cases and information services to support sustainable decision-making in the built environment.

The ACCORD project developed two tools to assist countries in the definition of the national strategy. The first is a BIM-based building permit digital maturity level with 4 steps in the maturity process, and the second is the roadmap methodology.

Figure 1. Digital Building Permits Maturity Levels - [Link](#)

Figure 2. Digital Building Permits Roadmap Methodology - [Link](#)

2.

Standardise an Interoperable Format for the Representation of Construction Regulatory Documents and Rules.

An interoperable format capable of representing regulatory documents and the rules contained within required standardisation and consensus within the construction sector. This will allow the development of common tools that can be used in the authoring of regulation, management of permitting processes and checking of permit submissions.

The ACCORD project developed a candidate for this standardisation in the form of the AEC3PO ontology, and its instantiation in the form of the ACCORD BCRL YAML-LD and JSON-LD machine-readable versions of the regulatory documents considered within the ACCORD project.

Figure 3. ACCORD Rule Formalisation Process - [Link](#)

3.

Formalise Machine-Readable Regulations and Building Codes

Policymakers should implement plans to formalise their own regulations and building codes not only into human-readable formats but also into machine-readable formats. This will ensure the rules are up-to-date, comprehensible, and aligned with national and international standards. It is fundamental to the development of appropriate processes and tools to manage this action.

The ACCORD project developed a rule formalisation tool to facilitate the creation of machine-readable rules from text-based regulations as part of the ACCORD semantic framework. This process utilises the *AEC3PO*, a semantic knowledge model designed by ACCORD to represent the data to make possible compliance processes in the construction industry. The AEC3PO ontology forms the specification for the ACCORD domain-specific rule language, the BCRL, which is utilised by the rule formalisation tool to generate rules in BCRL.

Figure 4. ACCORD Rule Formalisation Tool - [Link](#)

4.

Development of a National and Regional Rule Repository

Establish repositories containing machine-readable regulations and checking rules. The development and maintenance of repositories containing machine-readable regulations and checking rules are crucial for the effective implementation of ACCC. These repositories ensure that the regulations are accessible and usable in an open format by various stakeholders, including policymakers, service providers, and checker tool providers, guaranteeing a common standard at the national and regional level.

The ACCORD project developed an API specification and a open source implementation of a service that can as a repository for digitised construction regulations. This is built on top of GraphDB, utilises the ACCORD rule formalization process and is compatible with the accord rule formalization tool.

5.

Implementation of an interoperable BIM-Based Building Permit Framework Based on Open Standards

The BIM-based building permit framework should encompass semantic interoperability, ensuring that different systems can understand and utilise the data exchanged between them. The data exchanged originates from BIM, GIS, and other data sources. The framework should allow only open data transfer formats, such as IFC and BCF, supported by the IDS standard, to ensure interoperability between different systems and tools. The design data should be in IFC format, whereas the comments to the model are provided in BCF format. The standardised data formats ensure seamless interoperability between building and city models, between municipal and national levels, and for different purposes such as the DBL. Additionally, the establishment of an EIR between the building permit service and the authority's other information systems will facilitate the process.

ACCORD developed a semantic interoperable framework that acts as a blueprint for the implementation of BIM-based building permit and compliance checking.

Figure 5. ACCORD Semantic Interoperable Framework - [Link](#)

6.

Adoption of an Interoperable Cloud Architecture

Cloud architecture refers to the design framework that outlines the components, technologies, and services needed to develop, deploy, and manage applications within an intuitive and user-friendly cloud interface. For BIM-based building permit services, this architecture should be based on open service solutions that incorporate a diverse range of mature tools, processes, methods, and guidelines. BIM-based building permit services should support automated BIM model quality checks, including automated IFC data validation, as well as semi-automated code-compliance checks through integration with compliance services via open APIs. Furthermore, authorities and service providers must maintain a consistent and user-friendly digital tool environment to simplify the application process. Securing stored data through robust authentication technologies is also essential to protect sensitive information and preserve data integrity.

ACCORD developed a cloud architecture framework for the implementation of BIM-based building permit and compliance checking. The includes a set of open-source components that can be connected, as required by the building permitting processes for any given use-case.

Figure 6. ACCORD Cloud Architecture - [Link](#)

7.

Promote Stakeholder Collaboration

Foster collaboration among policymakers, building permit applicants, technology service providers, and permitting authorities to develop a unified National BIM-based building permit strategy and establish targeted maturity levels. Promote a participatory and multidisciplinary approach in designing BIM-based building permit strategies, processes, and guidelines to incorporate diverse perspectives, ensuring the needs of all stakeholders are addressed. Additionally, clearly define the roles and responsibilities of all actors involved in the BIM-based building permit process to enable effective coordination and collaboration, resulting in a more efficient, transparent, and sustainable building permit system.

Support the Transition with Use Case Harmonisation

Promote the harmonization of interfaces and the unification of digital solutions to ensure seamless interoperability across systems and stakeholders. Actively participate in and support standardisation initiatives to encourage pre-standardization efforts and the establishment of unified norms. Encourage applicants to align existing BIM laws and regulations with their BIM strategies, while also developing internal processes to efficiently produce BIMs that include all required, well-defined information for automated verification in digital building permitting.

Establish best practice examples and a clear framework to facilitate the integration of digital tools and processes among all stakeholders. Define key BIM use cases for permitting checks, including detailed tool-specific BIM guidelines for architects. Recognise that effective code-compliance checking requires adaptations in architects' modelling workflows, shifting focus from geometry alone to incorporating compliance-ready information into their designs.

ACCORD demonstrate the BIM-based permit application and automated compliance checking process in 13 use cases in 5 countries (Finland, Estonia, Germany, UK, Spain) using 12 current and future building regulations and 9 different real-life digital models of existing buildings, their structures or urban areas, resulting in a set of best practices from the perspective of the Authority and applicants.

Figure 7. ACCORD 13 Use Cases in 5 European Countries

9.

Provide Training and Competence Building

Invest in comprehensive training and capacity-building initiatives for all stakeholders involved in the BIM-based building permit process. Develop common guidelines and implement training programs focused on BIM, openBIM, model-based checking, and related technologies to bridge skill gaps and support the adoption of innovative tools. Provide state support and training assistance to ensure equitable access to education and resources across municipalities.

Prioritize the acquisition of new tools, including model viewing and inspection software licenses, 3D presentation technologies (such as virtual reality tools), and city model software, alongside establishing robust databases and detailed designer instructions. Establish a municipal HelpDesk to facilitate the adoption of information models and provide designers with guidance to enrich BIM models to meet permit requirements.

Address the geospatial knowledge gap among designers to ensure accurate model integration and enhance alignment with real-world contexts. Advocate for presenting materials to decision-makers to highlight the benefits and necessities of investing in training, tools, and digital transformation. Finally, build trust in digital tools by presenting them as supportive resources, offering tailored training to empower stakeholders and strengthen their competencies in using advanced technologies.

ACCORD delivered 20 e-learning materials plus a Educational Start Package in English translated in Estonia, French, Finnish, German and Spanish.

Figure 8. ACCORD Educational Start Package available at [ACCORD Zenodo Community](#)

10.

Secure Funding for Digital Transformation

Secure adequate funding to drive the digital transformation of building permit processes, focusing on the development, implementation, and maintenance of digital permitting platforms, compliance-checking tools, and stakeholder training programs. Establish dedicated Research & Development (R&D) initiatives to address key aspects, including the integration of BIM-based building permits with authorities' information systems, process reengineering, the creation of interoperable interfaces, and the development of essential skills.

Encourage authorities to actively monitor technological advancements and participate in innovation hubs to align R&D efforts with the goal of automating building permit processes. This approach will ensure the adoption of cutting-edge solutions and foster a seamless, efficient, and future-ready permitting system.

11.

Implement Feedback Loops and Continuous Improvement

Develop and establish feedback loops to support the continuous enhancement of the digital building permit process. Engage applicants, including architects and building owners, in pilot projects for process and software development to align with target performance and sustainability goals. This participatory approach will identify areas for improvement and ensure efficiency and effectiveness in the permitting process.

12.

Address Legal Issues Related to BIM Storage and Ownership

Incorporate clear regulations within the Building Act concerning the long-term storage, access rights, and ownership of BIM models following permit approval to ensure legal certainty. Address key legal issues such as digital signatures and model ownership during the digital lifecycle of BIM models. Mandate authorities to define the use and archival procedures of IFC-based designs through the Building Act and corresponding regulatory decrees.

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